

WorldCOM Deliverable 5.1 Report (D-JRP13-5.1) – Organisation of Project Kick-Off Meeting

The WorldCOM consortium attending the kick-off meeting in Brussels on January 28th. L-R Prof Dearbháile Morris (NUIG), Prof Roberto LaRagione (UoS), Dr Owen Higgins (NUIG), Dr Veljo Kisand (UoT), Prof Manuela Canica (INSA), Prof Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn (VISA-VET-UCM), Dr Vera Manageiro (INSA), Dr Christian Menge (FLI), Dr Louise O'Connor (NUIG), Dr Christian Berens (FLI), Dr Liam Burke (NUIG), Prof Terry Smith (NUIG – Project Coordinator).

Summary

The WorldCOM kick-off meeting was held on January 27th – 28th 2020 in the Maeterlinck Meeting Room, Eurostation II, Brussels. Every partner in the WorldCOM consortium was represented at the meeting (see attendee list above).

The One Health EJP Scientific Coordinator Hein Imberechts opened the meeting and provided an overview of the One Health EJP. The meeting agenda covered initial introductions, followed by sequential discussion of the work package tasks, with presentations from task leaders and their colleagues. Strategy and timing of the work to be carried out over the project was discussed, with a particular focus on priorities for the first 12 months. Project Management Team membership and partner reporting contacts were agreed. An update on researcher recruitment was provided by relevant partners. The policies and plans for communications, data management and scientific publications were agreed.